

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES IN OXIDATION-REDUCTION REACTIONS. PART XI. QUANTITATIVE POTENTIOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF AROMATIC AMINES.

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o-Nitroaniline, *p*-nitroaniline and 2 : 4-diaminophenol dihydrochloride have been estimated by titrating them potentiometrically against potassium iodate in presence of hydrochloric acid and *o*-phenylenediamine, *o*-aminophenol, *p*-aminophenol and diphenylamine against nitrous acid, using a platinum electrode coupled with a saturated calomel electrode at 15°.

The potentiometric method for the determination of the end-point in the titration of aromatic compounds with bromate in the presence of bromide has been applied by Callan and Horrobin (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1929, 47, 334). Singh and Singh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 346) used potassium chlorate and hydrochloric acid as a chlorinating agent in the potentiometric determination of aromatic compounds.

o-Nitroaniline, *p*-nitroaniline and 2 : 4-diaminophenol dihydrochloride can be chlorinated with potassium iodate in presence of hydrochloric acid and the reaction can be used for the potentiometric determination of these compounds.

When a solution of an aromatic amine is diazotised, free nitrous acid is formed at the completion of the reaction. A solution of nitrous acid in contact with a platinum electrode gives a definite potential. Muller and Dachselt (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1925, 31, 662) studied the titration of aniline, xylydine and aminoazobenzene disulphonic acid. They found that the potential requires some time to become steady during the titration. Attempts were made to accelerate the reaction using higher temperatures. It was found that at 20° or below, the results were accurate. It is not necessary, therefore, to cool the mixture in ice during the titration. Singh and Ahmad (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 16, 416) applied the diazotisation method in the estimation of aromatic amines at 15°.

Sodium nitrite, in presence of an acid, reacts with *o*-aminophenol, *p*-aminophenol and diphenylamine. The reactions are represented by the following equations :

When a dilute solution of sodium nitrite is added to a dilute solution of *o*-phenylenediamine, azoaminobenzene is formed according to the equation (Ladenburg, *Ber.*, 1887, 9, 221) :

The following equations represent the reactions between potassium iodate and *o*-nitroaniline, *p*-nitroaniline and 2 : 4-diaminophenol in presence of hydrochloric acid.

These reactions have been made use of in the quantitative estimation of *o*-nitroaniline, *p*-nitroaniline and 2 : 4-diaminophenol dihydrochloride and *o*-aminophenol, *p*-aminophenol, *o*-phenylenediamine and diphenylamine by the potentiometric method.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The oxidation-reduction electrode, which consisted of a bright platinum foil immersed in a solution to be titrated, was coupled with a saturated calomel electrode through an agar agar-potassium chloride bridge. The cell was placed in a water-bath the temperature of which was maintained at 15° E.M.F. of the cell was read on a potentiometer.

A known weight of the organic compound (*o*-nitroaniline, *p*-nitroaniline and 2 : 4-diaminophenol dihydrochloride) was mixed with water and a required amount of concentrated hydrochloric acid (Analar) was added to keep its concentration above 4*N*. The solution was titrated potentiometrically against standard potassium iodate solution. The mixture was kept stirred very thoroughly with a mechanical stirrer.

o-Phenylenediamine was titrated in presence of hydrochloric acid (Analar) and *o*-aminophenol, *p*-aminophenol and diphenylamine were titrated in presence of sulphuric acid (Analar), against standard sodium nitrite solution. On each addition of the titrant, the mixture was thoroughly stirred by means of a mechanical stirrer. The potentiometric readings were recorded 5 to 10 minutes after the addition of the reagent when the potential acquired a steady value.

A series of potentiometric titrations were performed with different amounts of each substance. One titration, as typical of each set, is recorded in the following tables,

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TABLE I.

0.0970 G. of *p*-nitroaniline mixed with 20 c.c. of water and 25 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid and titrated against *M*/20-potassium iodate.

KIO ₃	E.M.F.	E/C, (m. volt/c.c.)	KIO ₃ ,	E.M.F.	E/C, (m. volt/c.c.)
0'00 c.c.	0'470 volt	86	13'90 c.c.	0'727 volt	640
2'00	0'641	2	13'95	0'759	1620
5'00	0'648	3	14'00	0'840	(max.) 480
7'00	0'654	4	14'05	0'864	280
9'00	0'662	8	14'10	0'878	90
10'50	0'673	8	14'20	0'887	37
12'00	0'685	11	14'50	0'898	26
13'00	0'696	14	15'00	0'911	15
13'50	0'703	25	16'00	0'926	7
13'70	0'708	40	18'00	0'940	5
13'80	0'712	100	21'00	0'956	3
13'85	0'717	200	25'00	0'968	3
			30'00	0'981	

TABLE II.

0.1465 G. of *p*-aminophenol mixed with 30 c.c. of 30% sulphuric acid and titrated against *M*/₁₀-sodium nitrite.

NaNO ₂	E.M.F.	E/C. (m.volt/c.c.)	NaNO ₂	E.M.F.	E/C. (m.volt/c.c.)
0.00 c.c.	0.380 volt		13.375 c.c.	0.552 volt	
2.00	0.478	49	13.400	0.565	520
5.00	0.490	2	13.425	0.628	2520 (maximum)
8.00	0.496	2	13.450	0.640	480
9.50	0.499	2	13.500	0.659	380
11.00	0.508	6	13.700	0.680	105
12.00	0.516	8	14.000	0.692	40
12.50	0.521	10	14.800	0.705	16
12.80	0.524	10	16.000	0.710	4
13.00	0.527	15	17.000	0.712	2
13.10	0.529	20	19.000	0.712	—
13.20	0.532	30	21.000	0.698	—
13.30	0.535	30	24.000	0.689	—
13.35	0.542	140	29.000	0.682	—
		400			—

The titrations, one for each substance, are represented by the curves given in Fig. 1 and 2.

D I S C U S S I O N .

In these titrations, it is evident that for the first set, with the addition of standard potassium iodate solution, the E.M.F. rose steadily till the equivalence point. At the equivalence point there was a sharp jump in potential followed by a steady rise with further addition of the reagent.

In the second set, with the addition of standard sodium nitrite the E.M.F. rose steadily except in *o*-phenylenediamine, where it rose with the first addition of the reagent but with further addition the potential began to fall. This was followed by a steady rise till the equivalence point. At the equivalence point there was a sharp jump in potential in each case. After the equivalence point there was again a rise in the potential, followed by a steady fall.

From the volume of the titrant required in each titration, corresponding to the equivalence point, the amount of the amine was calculated. The values obtained are compared in the following tables with the amounts of the amine taken.

TABLE III.

<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline.		<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline.		2 : 4-Diaminophenol dihydrochloride.	
Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.
0'0917 g.	0'0915 g.	0'0970 g.	0'0967 g.	0'1001 g.	0'1005 g.
0'1133	0'1129	0'1408	0'1406	0'1562	0'1563
0'1958	0'1955	0'1891	0'1886	0'3127	0'3127
0'2918	0'2916	0'2816	0'2812	0'4731	0'4730
0'3855	0'3855	0'3918	0'3917	0'6276	0'6280

TABLE IV.

<i>o</i> -Aminophenol.		<i>p</i> -Aminophenol.		Diphenylamine.		<i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine.	
Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.
0'1294 g.	0'1293 g.	0'1465 g.	0'1462 g.	0'1943 g.	0'1940 g.	0'2216 g.	0'2215 g.
0'1858	0'1854	0'1973	0'1971	0'2933	0'2930	0'3513	0'3513
0'2333	0'2331	0'2932	0'2928	0'3928	0'3925	0'5039	0'5037
0'2827	0'2826	0'3920	0'3916	0'4942	0'4941	0'8599	0'8593
0'4198	0'4193	0'5397	0'5391	0'5840	0'5835	1'0002	1'0000
0'5854	0'5850			0'6929	0'6926		

These results show that *o*-nitroaniline, *p*-nitroaniline, 2 : 4-diaminophenol dihydrochloride, and *p*-aminophenol, *o*-aminophenol, diphenylamine and *o*-phenylenediamine can be determined quantitatively by the potentiometric method.

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